

The Role of History Taking and Technology in the Field of Gynecology

Rozmetova Roziyajon Yaqubboy Kizi

3rd-year student of Termiz branch of Tashkent Medical Academy in Surkhandarya region

Annotation: The most important thing is to ask the patient about your history. During the inquiry, the doctor will have the necessary information to think about the diagnosis of the disease.

On the basis of anamnesis data, it is possible to correctly diagnose 50-70% of diseases and prescribe further objective examinations.

After collecting the anamnesis, the woman will be examined. During the examination of a woman, we should also pay close attention to her height and weight, body structure, and the development of adipose tissue. There is a difference between male and female body structure.

Your anamnesis should be conducted according to the rules of procedure.

- 1) Main complaints.
- 2) Additional complaints

Complaints are often given after asking the doctor to inquire. Doctors should ask carefully and attentively. For example, young women complain of infertility, menstrual cycle disorders, weight gain or painful menstruation, nerves - they do not provide information about their mental illnesses, as well as what medications they take.

Women suffering from hemorrhagic diathesis (Werlhof's disease) take glucocorticoid drugs and complain of amenorrhea or oligomenorrhea, although these drugs in turn lead to such consequences. In cases of excess body weight, it is necessary to determine whether it was fattened from when: from childhood to puberty, from the beginning of sexual life, after abortion or childbirth. Each anamnesis has its place and importance. Correctly identifying all of them helps to treat the disease 70%

Key words: Gynecological anamnesis, hirsutism, acne, hysteroscopy, Laparoscopy, UTT, FDT, FKM.

Gynecological pains are mainly located in the hypogastric area. These iliac bones are located below the line connecting the anterior superior growths, and the legs are irradiated. Along with pains in the lower abdomen, lower back pains are also common. Diagnosis of gynecological diseases begins with a careful study of the anamnesis. Not only in gynecology, but in the treatment of all diseases, a careful examination of the patient and the anamnesis vita are of great importance, which helps to quickly and easily treat the disease.

Gynecological examination. Examination of the external and internal genitals provides important information in women with irregular menstrual cycles and infertile women. Hyperplasia of the labia majora and minora, paleness and dryness of the vaginal mucosa are considered signs of hypoestrogenism. "Sensitivity" of the mucous membrane, cyanotic color of the mucous membrane of the vulva, and the release of a large amount of clear secretion indicate a large amount of estrogen.

Family anamnesis is also very important. Taking into account the hereditary nature of many diseases, it is necessary to collect information about the presence of mental illnesses, endocrine disorders, tumors, pathology in the cardiovascular system in relatives belonging to the first, second and subsequent generations and important in treatment.

Hysteroscopy is one of the main advantages of this method, which gives the opportunity to identify intrauterine pathology.

Laparoscopy - examination of the pelvic and abdominal organs against the background of pneumoperitoneum. The abdominal cavity is examined by injecting SO₂, O₂ or air. With the help of laparoscopy examination, it is possible to distinguish the inflammatory processes of the uterus and appendices, and to determine the causes of acute abdominal symptoms.

Ultrasound is a method of examination using non-invasive devices, which helps to identify uterine diseases and tumors, diseases of the uterus, and defects in the development of the uterus. The latest models of diagnostic devices are highly effective, monitor the growth of follicles, ovulation, return the thickness of the endometrium, detect its hyperplasia and polyps.

In modern gynecology practice, radioimmunological analyzes are used to determine protein (luteotropin, follitropin, prolactin) and steroid hormones (estradiol, testosterone, cortisone) in blood plasma. One time determination of hormones and their metabolites in blood and urine gives little information. Colposcopy is widely used as an endoscopic method, as these tests allow to determine the functional state and reserves of the hypothalamus, pituitary gland, adrenal glands, ovaries and endometrium. This method helps to carefully examine the walls of the uterus and vulva.

Conclusion: Doctors should carefully examine and diagnose each disease. It is caused by viral and microbial diseases of internal organs. It is very important to test for every virus and germ, and it is very important to detect every disease.

It is very important to determine the sensitivity of the patient's body to antibiotics before using antibiotics in every disease. If we use strong antibiotics, weak antibiotics will not work. Therefore, every woman and girl should undergo a doctor's examination twice a year. Therefore, technologies should be checked very correctly.

Technologies should also be reviewed once a year. It is important to make a correct diagnosis. Every doctor is required to be attentive. Currently, the development of science and technology, the development and implementation of new research and treatment methods (endoscopy, ultrasound, computer tomography, nuclear magnetic resonance tomography, laparoscopy, laser beams, etc.). It causes the further development of medicine. This is the greatest achievement of our medicine. It has its place in the field of gynecology. Today's 21st century can be imagined without technologies. Our medicine is especially important in the field of gynecology. It helps the doctor to treat every disease easily and quickly. We must draw conclusions from experiments and apply our theoretical knowledge in practice. Then the knowledge we have learned will be strengthened and become a mature specialist in his field. Anamnesis collection and technology have an invaluable role in the accurate and clear examination of each patient.

Rozmetova Roziyajon Yaqubboy Kizi, was born on November 10, 2004 in Koshkopir district of Khorezm region. She is a 3rd year student of Termiz branch of Tashkent Medical Academy in Surkhandarya region. participated in the national anthology with the article "Ensuring sufficient personnel in the use and correction of technologies used in medicine". Participated in the Turkish international anthology with the articles "Importance of medical technologies in the field of gynecology" and "Using technologies in gynecology" and won the 1st place in the Nafosat competition. Studied more than 10 courses on medicine and personal development. Abroad and O In Uzbekistan, more than 10 articles have been published in prestigious magazines. His dream is to contribute to the development of Uzbekistan's medicine and receive the Zulfiya award.

References:

1. Social networks are used.
2. Obstetrics and gynecology nursing work book. Ya.N.Allayorov and R.Q. Askarva wrote.
3. Textbook of obstetrics and gynecology Kattakhodjoeva M.H.
4. A.G. Gadayev, propaedeutics of internal diseases M.Sh. Karimov H.S. Akhmedov.
5. Aylamazyan E.K. Obstetrics 2003
6. Orlov V.N. Moscow: Meditaina 1989
7. Melnichenko G.A.: Moscow "Geotar media"
8. Roytberg G.E Vinuterine diseases 2007
9. Roitberg G.E Vinuterine diseases 2001
10. Jabbarova YU.K. Ayupova F.M. - Obstetrics, Tashkent 2012.
11. Obstetrics, Saveleve G.M. Moscow 2002
12. Obstetrics and Gynecology. Pod redoksiya G.M. Savelevoy M. 2008.